

Fertilizer management

Effects of time of split application of K on soil N forms and lowland rice yield

D. Muthumanickam, M. Ravichandran, and M. V. Sriramachandrasekaran, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, 608002, India

An experiment was conducted to study the effect of timing of split application of K on N forms in the soil and on rice yield. The experiment was carried out using clay soil (Typic Chromusters. pH 8.04, electrical conductivity 0.32 dS m⁻¹, organic carbon 0.41 % and 294, 10, 290 kg available NPK ha⁻¹). The crop received 100-22-41.5 kg NPK ha⁻¹. Half of the N and K and the entire dose of P were applied basally. The remaining amount of N and K was equally split and topdressed as per treatment schedule (see table).

The experiment was carried out in two different seasons (February to June and July to November) using IR20 and a factorial completely randomized block design. Treatments were replicated thrice. Twelve replications were used (three replications at each stage of soil analysis).

Soil samples were taken at a depth of 15 cm during tillering, panicle initiation, flowering, and harvest stages. Wet soil samples were analyzed for NH₄-N, NO₃-N, available N, and fixed NH₄-N. Plants collected at harvest were threshed carefully to separate the grains and straw and weighed separately after drying at 60 °C.

In both seasons, grain and straw yields were highest when K was always applied 7 d earlier than N (see table). Yields were lowest in the control and when K was applied 7 d after N (see table). The higher grain and straw yield with early application of K was caused by the greater availability of NH₄-N and NO₃-N at tillering and panicle initiation (see figure),

Light micrographs of rice embryo tissues, showing intercellular spaces among the cells. A low magnification view of the radicle and mesocotyl regions of a mature embryo (a); higher profiles of the radicle procortex region (b); inner coleoptile cells (c) in dry seeds; inner scutellar parenchyma cells 48 h after imbibition (HAI) (d); meristematic cortical cell region of seminal root (e); and a lower view of the root (f), 72 HAI; apical region of the root tip, 96 HAI (g); and meristematic cells of the cortex, 120 HAI (h). d-h: nonsubmerged condition. Arrows indicate intercellular spaces. Bar = 50 μ m.

Effect of time of split application of K on grain and straw yield (t ha⁻¹) of rice.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield		Straw yield	
	Feb-Jun	Jul-Nov	Feb-Jun	Jul-Nov
Control (T1)	3.4	3.3	4.8	4.4
Entire basal K (T2)	4.4	4.4	6.6	6.4
K 7d earlier than N at T and PI (T3)	6.5	6.4	8.2	8.1
K + N at T and PI (T4)	5.1	4.9	7.0	6.7
K 7d after N at T and PI (T5)	3.8	3.6	5.3	5.0
K 7d earlier than N at T and K + N at PI (T6)	5.7	5.5	7.2	7.0
K 7d earlier than N at T and K 7d after N at PI (T7)	5.1	4.9	7.6	7.4
K + N at T and K 7d earlier than N at PI (T8)	5.2	5.0	7.3	7.1
K + N at T and K 7d after N at PI (T9)	4.3	4.1	6.6	6.3
K 7d after N at T and K 7d earlier than N at PI (T10)	4.2	4.0	6.5	6.1
K 7d after N at T and K + N at PI (T11)	4.2	4.0	6.7	6.4
CD (p = 0.05)	0.544	0.405	0.834	0.625

^a T = tillering, PI = panicle initiation, K + N = joint application of K and N.

Grain yield was positively correlated with NH₄-N at maximum tillering in the February-June ($Y = 1.51 \times -1.85$, $r = 0.89^{**}$) and July-November seasons ($Y = 1.49 \times -1.91$, $r = 0.91^{**}$). Application of K before N presumably suppressed fixation of NH₄⁺ from applied fertilizer

because selective exchange sites in the 2:1 layer clay minerals were occupied by K⁺. On clay soils with high K⁺ and NH₄⁺ fixation potential, rice yields and N recovery efficiency can be increased by applying K fertilizer 1 wk before N topdressing. ■

Changes in ammoniacal (a), nitrate (b), and available nitrogen (c) due to time of split application of potassium.

Effect of Biozyme and NPK on rice yield

A. Sen and K. Santosh, Agronomy Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Varanasi 221005, Uttar Pradesh, India

Biozyme is a commercial product produced from *Ascophyllum nodosum*, a seaweed alga known to be rich in cytokinin and auxin precursors, enzymes, and hydrolyzed protein. Farmers apply it in the field to enhance growth and yield of crop by effecting better utilization of nutrients.

We conducted a field trial during the 1993-94 wet season to investigate the effect of Biozyme granules in combination with NPK on yield performance of rice at the BHU research farm. The trial consisted of nine treatments: control (i.e., no Biozyme or NPK) (T1); 15 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 120-60-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (100% fertilizer) (T2); 15 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T3); 20 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer (T4);

20 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T5); 40 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer (T6); 40 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T7); 50 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer (T8); and 50 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T9).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. N, P, and K were applied as urea, diammonium phosphate, and muriate of potash, respectively. All of the P, K, and Biozyme were applied basally, while N was applied in three splits (in 1:2:1 ratio) during transplanting, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation. In treatments 6, 7, 8, and 9, Biozyme was applied in two equal splits, at transplanting and 30 d after transplanting (DAT).

The variety was Early Monsoori, a medium-duration cultivar. Soil was slightly alkaline (pH 7.4), has low available N (210 kg ha⁻¹) and P (11 kg ha⁻¹) but medium K (179 kg ha⁻¹) content, and 0.32% organic C. The field was kept flooded throughout the growing period.

All treatments recorded significant increases in number of spikelets panicle⁻¹, panicles m⁻², and grain and straw yield over the control in both years. An increase in yield with an increasing dose of Biozyme + fertilizer was observed up to the 40 kg Biozyme + 100% fertilizer ha⁻¹ treatment, after which a decreasing trend was noted. T6 produced a significantly superior yield compared with T2 and T3; the rest remained statistically on par with each other. It was further observed that the yield gap between 100 and 50% fertilizer doses along with different doses of Biozyme was considerably reduced. A similar trend was also found in all other yield-attributing characters. The stimulatory effect of Biozyme was most probably due to the presence of cytokinin and auxin precursors, which resulted in elevated cellular energy and more effective tillering. The addition of Biozyme at 20 kg ha⁻¹ with 50% of the recommended NPK dose could save as much as Rs 690.35 ha⁻¹ over 100% fertilization. ■